

TECHNOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING IN PRIMARY CLASSES

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Abstract. This article discusses the technology for the development of critical thinking and describes its positive aspects. The expediency of using this technology in primary classes is revealed.

Keywords: critical thinking, primary schoolchildren, pedagogical technology, teaching, upbringing.

INTRODUCTION

At the moment, a wide variety of technologies are being used in the world. New technologies are constantly being developed, some of which are immediately actively used in practice. One of the currently popular technologies is the technology for the development of critical thinking, developed at the end of the 20th century in the USA by such teachers as C. Temple, D. Steele, K. Meredith. In it they combined the ideas of domestic technologies of collective and group teaching methods, the technology of cooperation and the technology of developmental education, which makes the technology of developing critical thinking a supra-subject matter y.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

This technology is an integral system that involves the formation of skills in working with information in the process of reading and writing. The tasks that are solved in the process of using this technology can be identified as: the task of educational motivation, which involves increasing the level of interest in learning, learning self-education and self-control skills, developing the ability to work independently; the task of writing culture, aimed at developing the ability to write texts in any genre; the task of information literacy, including the formation of the

ability to independently analyze and evaluate information of any level of complexity, the development of the ability to navigate in the diversity of information readers of information and use various reading strategies, adequately perceive what is read, sort information by degree of importance, draw conclusions and generalize; the task of social competence, which involves the development of communication skills and responsibility for knowledge [3, p. 219].

RESULTS

Fruitful work within the framework of this technology will make it possible to prepare students who will be able to become valuable members of society in the future, i.e. They will be able to work, try to do with other people with other people, to reduce tolerance, to initiate solutions, to stir up and relay ideas, to have been reduced and able to get out of the ponds in. To achieve all this, children need to work actively and be able to bring their own curiosity and desire to find meaning in everything into the learning process. The technology for the development of critical thinking presupposes a non-standard approach to understanding things, teaches children to speak out, listen and be heard, be able to participate in disputes and competently come out of any dispute.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Many teachers choose this technology, as it is designed to educate a strong and educated personality. Each student in this technology learns to stand up for his own opinion and listen to others. He himself formulates his ideas and assessments, regardless of the criticism or wishes of others. This technology has that freedom that allows students not to be afraid that they will be judged or misunderstood, because here no one is embarrassed to speak and there is always support and attention from the team. Children can agree or disagree with the opinion of another, they can accept or not accept his point of view, they can change or defend their own to the last - they have no restrictions in this regard. The technology is aimed specifically at the

educational aspect of education, without forgetting about the learning itself [1, p. 124].

In this technology, information is only the starting point of critical thinking, which should encourage students to learn more and more about it, to strive for self-education. Knowledge gives motivation to think critically. In order for an opinion or idea to form to the required level, you need to thoroughly study all sides of the issue, which is what students are directed to do by receiving minimal information in class. Children themselves can decide what specifically interests them more and what they should pay attention to in order to make their own decision.

Critical thinking helps children pose and find solutions to questions that concern them. People are very curious by nature, and especially children of primary school age who are just beginning to comprehend the world and want to know how this or that process in the world works. This technology helps them learn not to receive incomplete or inaccurate information from others, but to find the information they need independently, without outside help. This helps them acquire the maximum amount of knowledge on this or that issue and satisfy their interest, build a logical chain and continue to delve into the subject of their interest.

Another side of the technology for the development of critical thinking is its focus on the argumentation of one's opinion. The student must learn not only to express his point of view, but also to prove it using the data that he has found on this issue. This helps not to blindly choose a close opinion for yourself, but after studying all sides of the issue in detail, to come to the only correct decision for yourself, because often in the process of studying a topic, people find information that is actually about contradicts their vision[2, p. .17].

CONCLUSIONS

It is enough to carry out similar work 2-3 times for this technique to become technologically advanced. Students enjoy using clusters. Tips for working with "bunches": Evaluate the text you will be working with. Is a breakdown into

“clusters” necessary in this case? Is it possible to identify large and small semantic units in the text? Help the student, if he has any doubts, to identify such semantic units. These could be questions or keywords, phrases. Sound out “bunches.” Have students make a presentation of their notes.

Ask to establish connections between the “branches” of your “bunch” and explain the connections that have arisen. If you want to stop at some semantic block, ask to make this branch brighter. The use of these techniques in reading lessons allows you to get very good results, since different sources of information are used, different types of memory and perception are involved.

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